

Unveiling Transparency: An Empirical Analysis of Voluntary Disclosure Practices in the Indian Banking Sector

Paper Id : 18913 Submission Date : 10/05/2024 Acceptance Date : 22/05/2024 Publication Date : 25/05/2024

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.11409147

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/innovation.php#8>

Rajani Gupta

Assistant Professor
Department Of Commerce
DDU Govt. Degree College
Gorakhpur, Uttar Pradesh,
India

Arvind Kumar

Senior Most Professor
Department Of Commerce
University Of Lucknow
Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh,
India

Abstract

Transparency and disclosure play an essential role in the Indian banking sector serving as key elements in fostering trust and confidence among depositors, investors and regulators. Voluntary disclosure provides in-depth information about financial and non-financial aspects which is very significant for the stakeholders in their decision-making process. In this research paper, the researchers have tried to provide an empirical analysis of voluntary disclosure practices in the Indian Banking Sector, shedding light on the extent, determinants and consequences of voluntary disclosure. This study will employ a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods to analyze the data collected from various banks (Public and Private sector) in India, providing a comprehensive overview of voluntary disclosure practices within the Indian Banking Industry. The study encompasses top six commercial banks of which, three from public sector (SBI, PNB and Bank of Baroda) and three from private sector (HDFC, ICICI and Axis bank). Charts, diagrams, descriptive statistics, content analysis etc has been used to support the study. The findings of the study will not only enhance our understanding of why and how the public and private sector banks are disclosing their information voluntarily but also provide valuable insights for bank management, policy makers and regulators. At the end, this study aims to give its contribution to the ongoing efforts to improve transparency and disclosure in the Indian Banking sector, which is fundamental aspect for maintaining financial stability and fostering trust of stakeholders.

Keywords

Voluntary Disclosure Practices, Stakeholders, Indian Banking Sector, Transparency and Disclosure, Financial Stability etc.

Introduction

In order to disclose the results of a corporate enterprise's business activities, corporate financial reporting in annual reports is a means of communication between the management and the user-groups of the financial statements. Additionally, it aims to prove the credibility, accountability, and reliability of its disclosures. Corporate financial reporting has two components in the "Indian" context: statutory (mandated) and non-statutory (optional/voluntary) disclosures.

I. Statutory Disclosure: Legal disclosures: In India, under clause 49 of the listing guidelines, both the company act and the securities and exchange rules, established by the SEBI, must be complied with. "The basic requirements for disclosure and reporting applicable to all corporations (or companies) incorporated in India" are provided by the company act. According to the law, corporations must create financial statements that present a "true-and-fair" picture of the financial situation. The statute mandates that all organizations keep specific sets of books of account for recording financial transactions and periodically publish their annual accounts in the format specified.

II. Non-statutory (voluntary) Disclosures: According to the Securities and Exchange Commission, voluntary disclosures are "at par in importance with statutory disclosure to give the complete idea of the corporations business and future prospects." Items of voluntary disclosure can be categorized into items that are historical, current, and prognosticative depending on the past, present, or future performance of the business. It is 'discretionary' to share information, nevertheless. Information provided in the yearly

reports that is not required by law and is entirely voluntary. It centred on the corporation's disclosure policy.

The management uses a variety of sources, including prospectuses, press releases, newspapers, magazines, websites, etc., to share information about the bank's performance and upcoming policies and programs. Despite these, the annual report of banks is acknowledged as the most significant source for both financial and non-financial information. The degree of disclosure's sufficiency cannot be measured accurately, but it can be assessed in relation to the needs, demands, and goals of the users. Buzby (1974) believes that five factors are obligatory to recognize the true nature of adequate disclosure. Questions that need to be addressed include:

1. for whom is the information to be disclosed?
2. What is the purpose of the information?
3. How much information should be disclosed?
4. How should the information be disclosed?
5. When should the information be disclosed?

The Concept of Voluntary Disclosure

Voluntary disclosure in corporate reporting represents a fundamental aspect of a firm's communication with its stakeholders beyond what is required by regulatory mandates. It involves the dissemination of information beyond the minimum legal requirements, typically through financial reports, press releases, sustainability reports, and various other mediums. Voluntary disclosure is pivotal in building trust, enhancing corporate governance, and ensuring transparency and accountability in the corporate world.

Fig. 1 Theoretical Foundations

i. Agency Theory: As per principle of agency, managers are given power by shareholders (the principals) to govern the organization on their behalf. Due to conflicting interests, this delegation, however, results in a principal-agent issue. It is believed that voluntary disclosure can reduce this information asymmetry by bringing agents' interests into line with the principals.

ii. Signalling Theory: As per signalling theory, managers can reduce uncertainty and information asymmetry by using voluntary disclosure to share important information with stakeholders. Firms utilize disclosures to influence stakeholders' opinions and decisions by sending signals about their financial standing, prospects for the future, or managerial skill.

iii. Stakeholder Theory: Stakeholder theory emphasizes the prominence of considering a broader range of stakeholders beyond stockholders, encompassing staff members, clients, vendors, and the general public. Voluntary disclosure in this context is viewed as a mechanism to demonstrate corporate social responsibility, responsiveness to stakeholder concerns, and sustainable business practices.

Determinants of Voluntary Disclosure

Similar to every industry, the Indian banking sector is affected by a variety of factors that fall under the classifications of internal and external determinants. These factors are essential to comprehending why and how many Indian banks opt to voluntarily provide information beyond what is necessary by law. It's crucial to keep in mind that these drivers may alter over time depending on how essential they are and how much of an impact they have on the market, the economy, and organizational strategies. Some crucial factors of voluntary disclosure in Indian banking sector are as follows:

Fig.2 Determinants of Voluntary Disclosure

i. Firm Characteristics: The volume and type of voluntary disclosure depends on a number of firm-specific factors. Bigger companies with greater resources and visibility generally make more voluntary disclosures. Additionally, the level of voluntary disclosure is significantly influenced by profitability, leverage, growth possibilities, and industry type.

ii. Regulatory Environment: The volume and type of voluntary disclosures are greatly influenced by the regulatory environment. Companies that operate in highly regulated sectors or in nations with strict reporting requirements may make more voluntary disclosures in order to comply with the law and societal norms.

iii. Corporate Governance: Greater voluntary disclosure is often encouraged by exemplary corporate governance standards, which include independent boards, active audit committees, and efficient internal control systems. Strong governance frameworks increase accountability and transparency, encouraging businesses to voluntarily reveal more information.

iv. Market Competition and Structure: Voluntary disclosure procedures in India are influenced by both the level of market competition and the banking sector's organizational structure. Banks may expand disclosure to obtain a competitive edge, foster investor confidence, and improve their market standing.

v. Financial Performance and Health: To demonstrate their monetary steadiness and health, banks may voluntarily provide information on their financial performance, capital sufficiency, asset quality, and liquidity positions. Increased investor confidence and possible investor interest can result from transparent reporting.

vi. Pressure from Stakeholders: Banks may raise their voluntary disclosures in response to pressure from stakeholders such as investors, analysts, customers, and civil society. It is essential for sustaining good relationships and reputations to satisfy the information demands and expectations of these stakeholders.

Need of Disclosure in Banking Sector

Most people would agree that the annual report is the most crucial tool for communicating with investors. The degree of adequate disclosure in the yearly reports could be a significant factor in determining the calibre of investment decision-making specifically, and distribution of economic resources overall. Despite the fact that these reasons apply to all types of organizations, financial institutions have failed to give them enough consideration up to this point. It is widely acknowledged that banks' reporting standards still fall short of those of non-financial firms (Kahl & Belkaoui, 1981).

Commercial and development banks are examples of business enterprises. Instead of manufacturing goods, they create and market financial services. They are referred to as financial intermediaries or financial institutions in this way. They carry out the role of middleman by pooling surplus resources from the sector of saving surplus and direct them toward the sector of saving deficit. A bank's problems impact the community as a whole. They rely on confidence to survive, and the strongest indication of that confidence is sound financial standing. They must always demonstrate that there is not even a hint regarding their financial situation. This explains why unique rules for the creation and presentation of bank financial statements are included in banking laws across the globe.

Therefore, banks are a vital component of a nation's financial system, and the economy depends on them being healthy. Furthermore, the fact that most individuals deposit their money in banks and the degree of confidence that these institutions require means that the good method of disclosure for banks.

Impact and Benefits of Voluntary Disclosure

The annual report is typically seen as being the most momentous form of stockholder communication. The degree of disclosure adequacy in the annual reports may play a major role in determining the usefulness of economic resource allocation in general and

investment decision making in particular. The impact and benefits of voluntary disclosure are as follows-

Fig. 3 Benefits of Voluntary Disclosure

i. Market Valuation: According to previous researches, businesses that make broad voluntary disclosures typically see their stock prices rise and their investor base grow more confident. Stock prices and trading volumes may be favourably impacted by clear and transparent communication.

ii. Cost of Capital: Investors may perceive lesser risk and better credibility as a result of transparent disclosure methods, which can cut the cost of capital and potentially lower the required rate of return.

iii. Stakeholder Relations: By demonstrating a commitment to transparency, voluntary disclosure improves connections with stakeholders and builds the firm's reputation and confidence with a variety of stakeholder groups. With regard to stakeholders, a voluntary disclosure practice plays a significant role because it generates high-quality both non-financial and financial data that is helpful for stakeholders to make decisions. As a result, it is essential that every bank make timely and complete disclosures in the annual reports of the banks (Shailaja B. 2021)

Objective of study

The following are the study's objectives:

1. To investigate the voluntary disclosure policies of specific Indian commercial banks.
2. To investigate and contrast the voluntary disclosure practices of selected Indian banks in the public and private sectors.

Review of Literature

Collett and Hrasky (2005) examined the connections between firms' intentions to seek capital on the financial markets and their voluntary disclosure of CG information. 299 companies from the "Australian" stock markets were included in the sample. According to the research, "just 29 Australian firms made optional CG disclosure, with different corporations disclosing different amounts of information.

Corporate transparency is essential for addressing knowledge asymmetry and minimizing agency issues. In instance, businesses can reduce capital costs, boost investor trust, and enhance the marketability of their shares by disclosing both required and optional information to the capital market. (Meek et al., 1995, Kristandl and Bontis, 2007).

The disclosure of governance information by the "Canadian" banks was the subject of a study conducted by **Maingot and Zeghal in 2008**. The authors concentrated on disclosing the CG practices utilized by eight institutions. According to their data, "the bigger the bank, the more disclosure there is. Overall, their findings imply that management's strategic considerations have an effect on the decisions about what information to publish and how much. In a further study, **Hossain and Hammami (2009)** empirically analysed the factors that contributed to voluntary disclosure in the AR of 25 listed companies on the Doha Securities Market in "Qatar." Multiple regression analysis was used for statistical analysis after developing a disclosure checklist with 44 voluntary elements of information. They conclude that "age, size, complexity, and assets-in-place are significant and other variable profitability is insignificant in explaining the level of voluntary disclosure".

By enhancing corporate governance and transparency through the use of voluntary disclosure systems, businesses are undoubtedly able to draw in more potential investors, increasing their investment appeal on the global market. (**Bhasin, Rashid R. & Orzalin. 2012**)

A key component of the "modern" corporate-regulatory system is corporate governance disclosure, which involves making "governance" information available to the public in a variety of ways. The voluntary CG practices of 50 firms are examined in this study in addition to the mandatory section 49 of the listing agreement criteria. A "content analysis" was conducted in order to analyze the voluntary CG disclosure procedures, and then a "CG disclosure" index was created. Corporations from the software, textiles, sugar, and paper industries have been chosen in order to provide a comparison "across" industries. The finding of this research reveals that Corporations are following less than half of the items of CG disclosure index. (**Bhasin, M.L. and Shaikh, J.M. 2013**).

The factors influencing companies to disclose voluntary information in their annual reports of Textile Manufacturing Companies in Bangladesh were examined by **Rouf, et.al (2014)** in their research paper titled "Financial Reporting Practices in the Textile Manufacturing Sectors of Bangladesh." The link between the dependent variable and the independent variables was investigated using an ordinary least squares (OLS) regression model. For the study, a voluntary index comprising 68 elements was created. The study's findings show a strong correlation between total assets and voluntary disclosure, as well as a favourable correlation between board size and voluntary disclosure. Additionally, it displays that the proprietorship structure is negatively correlated with the degree of voluntary disclosure.

Hawashe (2016) measured the degree of voluntary information disclosure in Libyan commercial banks' annual reports that are listed and those that are not in his article titled "Voluntary Information Disclosure in the Annual Reports of Libyan's Commercial Banks: A Longitudinal Analysis Approach." To look for any appreciable changes in the levels of voluntary disclosure in the annual reports, longitudinal analysis is used. A 63-item voluntary disclosure index was created. The findings show that corporate social information is the bottom level of voluntary disclosure in annual reports; on the other hand, the level with the greatest number of voluntary disclosures over the periods is background information.

Mangala D & Isha (2019) have looked at how much information is disclosed in annual reports of Indian stock market companies. To gauge the degree of transparency in chosen corporations' annual reports, seven disclosure indices have been developed. The analysis finds that, the average disclosure score across all information categories, with the exception of corporate financial data improved between 2008-09 and 2017-18. The maximum mean disclosure score through all categories for the whole study period is for the corporate governance data. The least amount of information is reported in the group of forward-looking information in company annual reports. Due to greater corporate knowledge and responsible reporting standards employed by the corporations, year-over-year overall transparency has also increased.

Saha, R., & Kabra, K. C. (2022) The top-listed corporations in India were the focus of the researchers' investigation of the impact of voluntary disclosure on market value. To accomplish this, a sample of the top 100 non-financial and non-utility companies listed on the Bombay Stock Exchange over a five-year period (2014-2018) is used in the study. The analysis's findings indicate that a greater level of voluntary disclosure greatly raises the market value of the sample companies. The study goes on to analyze voluntary disclosure further by breaking it down into its sub-components. The results show that three voluntary disclosure sub-components, such as corporate and strategic disclosure, forward-looking disclosure, and corporate governance disclosure, positively affect firms' market values, while the remaining sub-components, such as human and intellectual capital disclosure and financial and cap Overall, the result indicates that investors believe the voluntary disclosure deemed relevant by the sample companies.

V.R Naveenan & etal, (2024) in their research article entitled "Analyzing corporate disclosure in Indian banks: assessing compliance, corporate attributes, and performance implications" stated that for many stakeholders to make the best judgments possible, corporate disclosure is essential. Depending on the characteristics of the company, disclosure policies may differ. Their research focuses on examining how business characteristics affect disclosure. This research article reaffirms that banks ought to be open and cognizant of the importance of information disclosure and corporate qualities. It promotes corporate disclosure as crucial, as it helps practitioners and policymakers win over stakeholders' trust, which opens up business prospects and sheds light on the bank's operations.

Research Gap

As the literature review above makes clear, research on voluntary disclosure has been done in extensive detail in the past and there is still more to learn. It is considerable that numerous studies have been conducted in both developed and developing countries on

voluntary disclosure in corporate sector. Very few researches have carried out to provide an empirical analysis of voluntary disclosure practices in the Indian Banking Sector, illuminating the scope of determinants and consequences of voluntary disclosure. Hence, in this research paper, the researchers have tried to provide an empirical analysis on the voluntary disclosure in Indian Banking sector.

Hypothesis H0: The voluntary disclosure practices of Indian banks in the public and private sectors do not differ greatly from one another.

H1: The voluntary disclosure practices of Indian banks in the public and private sectors are differing greatly from one another.

Methodology i. **Data Sources:** Secondary data provide the basis of the current investigation. For the research analysis, annual reports of the selected banks (top three public and private sector) were collected from their official websites.

Sampling **Sampling Technique:** Purposive sampling method has been applied for the current study. Out of the six largest commercial banks in India, the top three banks from both the public and private sectors have been selected which are as follows.

Period of the Study: The study's time range is three financial years i.e., 2020-21, 2021-22 & 2022–2023. For investigation, annual reports of the selected banks were downloaded/ collected from their websites.

Analysis **Data Analysis Methods:** Top Indian commercial banks have employed content analysis to clarify their voluntary disclosure procedures. The voluntary disclosure index has been created and examined for this purpose.

Voluntary Disclosure Index Construction: The information items chosen and supplied voluntarily by selected banks in their websites or annual reports serves as the initial step in the creation of the voluntary disclosure index. A Basel III norm is also a comprehensive package of reform initiatives to improve regulation, supervision, and risk management. Pillar 3 of Basel III has been taken into consideration for the purpose of analysing information that is voluntary. For the analysis, ten variables in all have been chosen. Hence, overall number of voluntary disclosures for the study is 154 items, as in (Shailaja B. 2021).

Table: 1 Voluntary Disclosure Variables Index (Post-Basel III)

Sr. No.	Voluntary Variables Disclosure	No. of Items	Percentage
1	General Information about banks	6	3.9
2	Corporate Governance Information	5	3.25
3	Information related to employees	3	1.95
4	Important non-financial statistics	8	5.19
5	General Risk Management	5	3.25
6	Corporate Social Disclosure	11	7.14
7	Disclosure regarding committee	10	6.49
8	Financial performance information	9	5.84
9	Basel III, Pillar 3 Disclosures	92	59.74

10	Miscellaneous	5	3.25
	Total	154	100

Source: annual reports and website of concerned banks

Calculating the Voluntary Disclosure Index: In light of this research, the weighted disclosure index was employed to calculate how much information was voluntarily disclosed. The unweighted technique assigns a score to each bank using a dichotomous process; a bank receives a "1" if an item is disclosed in the annual reports or website, and a "0" if it is not. Numerous previous empirical disclosure studies have employed this methodology. This strategy is predicated on the idea that all readers of business annual reports will value each piece of information in the disclosure index equally. Total voluntary disclosure index score (TVDIS) of each bank for the chosen study period is computed after scoring.

$TVDIS = \text{Total Disclosure Score Obtained} / \text{Maximum Obtainable Score.}$

Results and Interpretation

Three banks from the public and three from the private sectors comprise the top 6 commercial banks selected for this study. The study looked at the voluntary disclosure practices used by a group of the top 6 public and private sector banks during the study period. Additionally, the TVDIS and Mean disclosure scores are presented. The rank has also been provided appropriately.

The Post-Basel III Voluntary Disclosure Score, TVDIS percentage, and ranking of the public and private sector banks included in the study are all displayed in the following table-

Table:2 TVDIS of Selected Public and Private Sector Banks (Post-BASEL III)

Sr. No.	Name of Bank	Voluntary Disclosure items (154)				
		2020-21	2021-22	2022-23	Pooled VDIS%	Rank
1.	State Bank of India	150 (97.40)	150 (97.40)	151 (98.05)	97.61	1
2.	Punjab National Bank	146 (94.81)	147 (95.45)	149 (96.75)	95.67	2
3.	Bank of Baroda	141 (91.56)	142 (92.20)	144 (93.50)	92.42	3
4.	HDFC Bank	140 (90.91)	142 (92.20)	143 (92.85)	91.98	4
5.	ICICI Bank	138 (89.61)	140 (90.91)	142 (92.20)	90.90	5
6.	Axis Bank	135 (87.66)	136 (88.31)	139 (90.25)	88.74	6

Source: Compiled data from the annual report and website

The aforementioned table shows that during the study period, the TVDIS percentage of public sector banks was higher than that of private sector banks. The State Bank of India is in first place among all other banks and is ranked as such because it made the most voluntary disclosures throughout the time (97.61%), while Punjab National Bank is in second place and is responsible for 95.67% of voluntary disclosures. The third is Bank of Baroda with a 92.42 percent. Regardless of whether they are in the public or private

sectors, the State Bank of India leads all other banks. In terms of voluntary disclosures, all public sector banks outperform other studied private sector banks. In a similar vein, HDFC leads the study's private sector banks with a percentage of 91.98, followed by ICICI bank with a percentage of 90.90. With a percentage of 88.74, the Axis bank has the lowest ranking among all banks in the research.

Conclusion

In this study, the extent of India's private and public sector banks' voluntary disclosure procedures have been empirically investigated. Banks in the public sector release more data than banks in the private sector. In addition, when compared to private sector banks, public sector banks disclose voluntary information with greater transparency. The State Bank of India has the best disclosure rating over the course of the investigation. In contrast, Axis Bank had the lowest score among private sector banks in the survey when compared to other private sector banks. In comparison to the other private banks in the survey, HDFC Bank is more open with its information disclosure. The research period saw an expansion in voluntary disclosure policies. Additionally, private sector banks require focusing more on providing detailed information and increasing transparency in their banking operations.

References

1. Bhasin, Rashid R. & Orazalin. 2012. Determinants of Voluntary Disclosure in the Banking Sector: An Empirical Study. *International Journal of Contemporary Business Studies* Vol: 3, No: 3. March, 2012 ISSN 2156-7506
2. Bhasin, M.L. and Shaikh, J.M. (2013) 'Voluntary corporate governance disclosures in the annual reports: an empirical study', *Int. J. Managerial and Financial Accounting*, Vol. 5, No. 1, pp.79-105.
3. Bhimavarapu, Rastogi & Abraham. 2022. The Influence of Transparency and Disclosure on the Valuation of Banks in India: The Moderating Effect of Environmental, Social, and Governance Variables, Shareholder Activism, and Market Power. *J. Risk Financial Manag.* 2022, 15(12), 612; <https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm15120612>
4. Buzby, Stephen L., "The Nature of Adequate Disclosures", *The Journal of Accountancy*, April 1974, pp: 47.
5. Collett, P. and Hraskey, S. (2005) 'Voluntary disclosure of corporate governance practices by listed Australian companies', *Journal of Corporate Governance: An International Review*, Vol. 13, No. 2, pp.188-196.
6. Hawashe. 2016. Voluntary Information Disclosure in The Annual Reports of Libyan's Commercial Banks: A Longitudinal Analysis Approach, *European- American Journals*, Print ISSN: 2053-4086
7. Hossain, M. and Hammami, H. (2009) 'Voluntary disclosure in the annual reports of an emerging country: the case of Qatar', *Advances in Accounting, Incorporating Advances in International Accounting*, Vol. 25, No. 2, pp.255-265.
8. Kristandl, G., & Bontis, N. 2007. The impact of voluntary disclosure on cost of equity capital estimates in a temporal setting. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*. Vol. 8, Issue 4, pp. 577-594
9. Mangala D., Isha. 2019. Extant of Disclosure through Annual Reports: A Study of Indian Corporate Sector, *HSB Research Review*, Vol. 14 No. 1 & 2
10. Maingot, M. and Zeghal, D. (2008) 'An analysis of corporate governance information disclosure by Canadian banks', *Corporate Ownership & Control*, Winter, Vol. 5, No. 2, p.225.
11. Meek, G.K., Roberts, C., & Gray, S.J. 1995. Factors Influencing Voluntary Disclosure Annual Report Disclosures by U.S., U.K. and Continental European Multinational Corporations. *Journal of International Business Studies*. Vol.96, No.3, pp.555-572
12. Rouf A. M, et.al. Financial Reporting Practices in the Textile Manufacturing Sectors of Bangladesh ABC *Journal of Advanced Research*, Volume 3, No 2, pp. 57-68, 2014
13. Saha, R., & Kabra, K. C. (2022). Is Voluntary Disclosure Value Relevant? Evidence from Top Listed Firms in India. *Vision*, 26(4), 471-481. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0972262920986293>
14. Shailaja B. 2021. Voluntary disclosure practices- A comparative study of top public and private sector banks in India, *IJARIIIT*, ISSN: 2454-132X, Volume 7, Issue 2 - V7I2-1242
15. V.R Naveenan, et.al, (2024). Analyzing corporate disclosure in Indian banks: assessing compliance, corporate attributes, and performance implications, *General & Applied Economics*, <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2023.2297589>